

Information Sheet for Research Project

Bullying among nursing students at Sultan Qaboos University

You are invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide whether to take part, it is important for you to understand, why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully.

What is the purpose of the study?

A group of medical students is carrying out a survey to assess the Bullying among nursing students at Sultan Qaboos University. Moreover, they are trying to correlate the socio-demographic features of participants with their levels of bullying.

Why have I been invited to take part?

We are kindly requesting all nursing students at Sultan Qaboos University to complete this survey.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether to take part, taking part is voluntary. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. If you decide to take part, you are still free to withdraw at any time and without giving a reason.

What would I have to do?

If you decide to take part, the survey will take approximately 5 minutes to complete.

Confidentiality

All the information that is collected will be anonymous and kept strictly confidential. All details that can identify you will be removed before storing the data.

Thank you for taking the time to read this information sheet.

Consent form for Research Project

Bullying among nursing students at Sultan Qaboos University

Please tick the appropriate box:

- I have read and understood the project information sheet dated/...../.....
- I have been given the opportunity to ask questions about the project.
- I agree to take part in the project. Taking part in the project will include completing a survey/being interviewed.
- I understand that my taking part is voluntary; I can withdraw from the study at any time and I will not be asked any questions about why I no longer want to take part.
- I understand that my words may be quoted in publications, reports, web pages, and other research outputs but my name will not be used unless I requested.
- I understand that other researchers will have access to this data only and they should agree to preserve the confidentiality of that data and terms that I have specified in this form.

Name of the participant

Signature

Date

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Researcher

Signature

Date

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Section 1: Demographics

1.	Age (in years): <ul style="list-style-type: none"><input type="radio"/> 17 – 20.<input type="radio"/> 21 – 24.<input type="radio"/> 25 – 28.<input type="radio"/> Above 29.
2.	Nationality: <ul style="list-style-type: none"><input type="radio"/> Omani<input type="radio"/> Non-Omani
3.	Gender: <ul style="list-style-type: none"><input type="radio"/> Male<input type="radio"/> Female
4.	Where do you live? <ul style="list-style-type: none">AloneWith roommates / In a flatWith your own family
5.	Marital status: <ul style="list-style-type: none"><input type="radio"/> Single.<input type="radio"/> Married.<input type="radio"/> Widowed.<input type="radio"/> Divorced
6.	Year of study: <ul style="list-style-type: none"><input type="radio"/> Foundation<input type="radio"/> First<input type="radio"/> Second<input type="radio"/> Third<input type="radio"/> Fourth<input type="radio"/> Fifth<input type="radio"/> Sixth<input type="radio"/> Seventh<input type="radio"/> Other:.....
7.	Place of original residence: <ul style="list-style-type: none"><input type="radio"/> Muscat.<input type="radio"/> Dhofar.<input type="radio"/> Musandam.<input type="radio"/> Buraymi.<input type="radio"/> The Dakhiliyah.<input type="radio"/> The North Batinah.<input type="radio"/> The South Batinah.<input type="radio"/> The South Sharqiyah.<input type="radio"/> The North Sharqiyah.<input type="radio"/> The Dhahirah.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The Wusta. Other:
8.	<p>Father's education level</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Illiterate ○ Primary school ○ Secondary school ○ Diploma ○ Bachelor degree ○ Master ○ PhD ○ Others
9.	<p>Mother's educational level</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Illiterate ○ Primary school ○ Secondary school ○ Diploma ○ Bachelor degree ○ Master ○ PhD ○ Others
10.	<p>Family economic status (according to the National Centre for Statistics and Information, Oman, 2023)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Low: monthly income less than 500 OMR ○ Middle: monthly income between 500 and 1500 OMR ○ High: monthly income more than 1500 OMR
11.	<p>how would you rate your health?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Excellent ○ Very good ○ Good ○ Poor /Fair
12.	<p>How often do you use the internet?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Once a day / others ○ Multiple Times a Day
13.	<p>What methods do you usually use to access the internet?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Wi-Fi connection at SQU campus ○ Wi-Fi connection at Home ○ Personal mobile data ○ Wi-Fi hotspots from friends / family ○ Wi-Fi hotspots in public places

Section II: General Bullying

Have you ever been bullied at school?

- Yes
- No

Have you ever been bullied at home?

- Yes
- No

Have you ever experienced bullying at SQU during your study?

- Yes
- No

Have you witnessed bullying at SQU?

- Yes
- No

If yes, what was your reaction?

- Tried to interfere
- Not reacted in any way

Have you ever bullied other students?

- Yes
- No

Have you used any of the following to bully other students?

- Online video clips of them
- Chatroom
- Through friends
- Face to face messaging
- Picture messages

What makes you bully other students?

- Due to personal issues
- For fun
- To feel more powerful

Do you think there should be a law at SQU to protect students from bullying?

- Yes
- No

How often do you get bullied at SQU?

- Daily
- Weekly
- Monthly
- Once a year
- A few times during the academic term

Who has bullied you?

- Roommates
- SQU mates
- Hospital staff
- Administrative staff
- Teachers/ instructors

What type of bullying have you faced?

- Sexual
- Cyber
- Physical
- Mental or emotional
- Verbal

What are the negative effects of bullying on you?

- Fearfulness
- Feeling low
- Poor marks
- Change in appetite
- Disengagement
- Lack of motivation
- Difficulty concentrating in class
- Depression
- Hate and anger
- Nothing

Which of the following methods have been used to bully you?

- Online video clips of them
- Online video clips of you
- Chatroom
- Through friends

- Face to face messaging
- Picture messages

Where does bullying take place?

- Sports
- Corridors
- Laboratory sessions
- Resting rooms
- Cafeteria/coffee
- Other transport
- Cars
- In the buses
- Hospital
- Class rooms

What do think makes them bully you?

- Academic excellence
- Poor academic performance
- Exclusion from activities
- Appearance or personal traits
- Personal differences
- Due to your academic major

Have you complained about bullying?

- Yes
- No

If no, reasons for not complaining

- Not sure to whom to complain
- Fearfulness
- Hope it will stop itself
- Not important